

TYPES OF PROVERBS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6582377>

Xushboqova Matluba Choriyevna

*Uzbekistan state world languages university,
Master degree student, 238 group*

A proverb (from Latin: proverbium) is a traditional saying that expresses a perceived truth based on common sense or experience. Proverbs are often metaphorical and use formulaic language. Collectively, they form a genre of folklore.

Some proverbs exist in more than one language because people borrow them from languages and cultures with which they are in contact. In the West, the Bible (including, but not limited to the Book of Proverbs) and medieval Latin (aided by the work of Erasmus) have played a considerable role in distributing proverbs. Not all Biblical proverbs, however, were distributed to the same extent: one scholar has gathered evidence to show that cultures in which the Bible is the major spiritual book contain “between three hundred and five hundred proverbs that stem from the Bible,” whereas another shows that, of the 106 most common and widespread proverbs across Europe, 11 are from the Bible. However, almost every culture has its own unique proverbs.

Lord John Russell (c. 1850) observed poetically that a “proverb is the wit of one, and the wisdom of many.” But giving the word “proverb” the sort of definition theorists need has proven to be a difficult task, and although scholars often quote Archer Taylor's argument that formulating a scientific “definition of a proverb is too difficult to repay the undertaking... An incommunicable quality tells us this sentence is proverbial and that one is not. Hence no definition will enable us to identify positively a sentence as proverbial,” many students of proverbs have attempted to itemize their essential characteristics.

More constructively, Mieder has proposed the following definition, “A proverb is a short, generally known sentence of the folk which contains wisdom, truth, morals, and traditional views in a metaphorical, fixed, and memorable form and which is handed down from generation to generation”. Norrick created a table of distinctive features to distinguish proverbs from idioms, cliches, etc. Prahlad distinguishes proverbs from some other, closely related types of sayings, “True proverbs must further be

distinguished from other types of proverbial speech, e.g. proverbial phrases, Wellerisms, maxims, quotations, and proverbial comparisons.” Based on Persian proverbs, Zolfaghari and Ameri propose the following definition: “A proverb is a short sentence, which is well-known and at times rhythmic, including advice, sage themes and ethnic experiences, comprising simile, metaphor or irony which is well-known among people for its fluent wording, clarity of expression, simplicity, expansiveness and generality and is used either with or without change.”

There are many sayings in English that are commonly referred to as “proverbs”, such as weather sayings. Alan Dundes, however, rejects including such sayings among truly proverbs: “Are weather proverbs proverbs? I would say emphatically 'No!' The definition of “proverb” has also changed over the years. For example, the following was labeled “A Yorkshire proverb” in 1883, but would not be categorized as a proverb by most today, “as throng as Throp's wife when she hanged herself with a dish-cloth”. The changing of the definition of “proverb” is also noted in Turkish.

In other languages and cultures, the definition of “proverb” also differs from English. In the Chumburung language of Ghana, “anase are literal proverbs and akpare are metaphoric ones”. Among the Bini of Nigeria, there are three words that are used to translate “proverb”: ere, ivbe, and itan. The first relates to historical events, the second relates to current events, and the third was “linguistic ornamentation in formal discourse”. Among the Balochi of Pakistan and Afghanistan, there is a word batal for ordinary proverbs and bassittuks for “proverbs with background stories”.

There are also language communities that combine proverbs and riddles in some sayings, leading some scholars to create the label “proverb riddles”.

Different categorizations of proverbs have been proposed by different scholars. For the purpose of the present article two main categorizations will be presented. The first categorization is one outlined by Norrick, who analyzed a sample of the proverbs from the Oxford Dictionary of English Proverbs. He developed a more empirically oriented and less grandiose schematization that categorizes proverbs according to the type of figuration they use. He distinguished five types of figurative proverbs: synecdoche, metaphoric, metonymic, hyperbolic and paradoxical. It must be mentioned that in Norrick's words figurative proverbs have figurative meanings that differ from their literal meaning. These types will be explored on briefly:

A. Synecdoche Proverbs. The proverbs in which the literal reading and standard proverbial interpretation or SPI "stand in a relation of macrocosm to microcosm". These includes examples such as the early bird catches the worm, make hay while the sun shines, and Fair words break no bones. In these proverbs, the literal meaning is quite different from the figurative meaning.

B. Metaphoric Proverbs. In metaphoric proverbs, a nominal becomes metaphoric due to its interaction with another proverb constituent, or the nominal symbolize some characteristic attribute. An example of the first is, Favor will as surely perish as life and of the second, Fair play is a jewel.

C. Metonymic Proverbs. This type of proverb is based on association between something literally named and the thing intended. One example of a metonymic proverb is "who has a fair wife needs more than two eyes" in which the eye stands metonymically for the "sight".

D. Hyperbolic Proverbs. According to Norrick "hyperbole has traditionally been considered a rhetorical figure along with, if not quite of the same importance of synecdoche, metaphor and metonymy". In fact hyperbole counts as amplification. Amplification says more than necessary. For example the proverb "faint heart never won fair lady" is a hyperbolic proverb due to the existence of never in it.

E. Paradoxical Proverbs. Proverbs in which there is a contradiction or whose interpretation entails a logical contradiction are considered as paradoxical proverbs. In fact paradoxical proverbs have a "second interpretation". An example of paradoxical proverb is "fair is not fair, but that which please". The first clause of this proverb asserts a clear logical contradiction. The proverb "a man's house is heaven and hell as well" is a paradoxical proverb as well. [21]

There are also several types of proverbs describe below: Universal proverbs - on comparing proverbs of culturally unrelated parts of the world, one finds several ones having not only the same basic idea but the form of expression, i.e. the wording is also identical or very similar. These are mainly simple expression of simple observations became proverbs in every language.

Regional proverbs – in culturally related regions – on the pattern of loan-words – many loan-proverbs appear besides the indigenous ones. A considerable part of them can be traced back to the classical literature of the region's past, in Europe the Greco-Roman classics, and in the Far East to the Sanskrit and Korean classics.

Local Proverbs – in a cultural region often internal differences appear, the classics (e.g. the Bible or the Confucian Analects) are not equally regarded as a source of proverbs in every language. Geographical vicinity gives also rise to another set of common local proverbs. These considerations are illustrated in several European and Far-Eastern languages, as English and Korean.

Proverbs were always the most vivacious and at the same time the most stable part of the national languages, suitable competing with the sayings and aphorisms of outstanding thinkers. In the proverbs and sayings picturesqueness of national thinking was more vivid expressed as well as their features of national character.

The proverbs and sayings the paper of folklore which is short but deep in the meaning. They express the outlook of the amount of people by their social and ideal functions. Proverbs and sayings include themselves the some certain features of historical development and the culture of people.

The semantic sphere of proverb is very wide and cannot limit them. The proverbs describe the every branch of people's life. The fact is that proverbs and sayings are similar in meaning in spite of their diversity in form and language. While investigating on the given qualification theme we have analyzed proverbs on the semantic point of view. We have come across on the following noticeable themes, such as Motherland, Time, Knowledge, Beauty, Health, Work and a lot other different subjects. We have classified some example on the given topics:

Motherland

1. East or West home is best.
2. Every bird likes its own nest.
3. There is no place like home.
4. Never cast dirt into that fountain if which you have sometimes drunk.
5. Don't cut the bought you are standing on.

Time

1. Time and tide wait for no man.
2. Time cures all things.
3. Time flies.
4. Time is money.
5. Cost time is never found again.

Knowledge

1. To everything is to know nothing.
2. Soon learnt soon forgotten.
3. Live and learn.

4. It's never too late to learn.
5. A little knowledge is a dangerous thing.

Beauty

1. All that glitters is not gold.
2. Appearances are deceptive.
3. Handsome is as handsome does.
4. There is no rose without the thorn.

Health

1. An apple a day keeps the doctor away.
2. A sound mind in a sound body.
3. Early to bed and early to rise makes a man health's, wealth's wise.
4. Good health is above wealth.
5. Health is not valued till sickness comes.

Work

1. A bad workman always blames his tools.

It might be wise to mention here at least some of the English proverbs which in themselves are folk definitions of a sort: “A good maxim is never out of season”; “All the good sense of the world runs into proverb”; “Proverbs are the children of experience”; “Proverbs are the wisdom of the streets”; “Nothing can beat a proverb”; “Proverbs cannot be contradicted”; “Though the old proverb be given up, it is none the less true”; “The old saying cannot be excelled”; “The wisdom of the proverb cannot be surpassed”; “Common proverb seldom lies”; “The old saying, long proved true, shall never be belied”; “Old saws speak truth”; “Every- proverb is truth”; “Old proverbs are the children of truth”; “What everyone says is true”; etc.

It appears that to the mind of proverb users, i.e. the general population, the proverb contains a good dose of common sense, experience, wisdom and above all truth. Certain principles and conditions of everyday life are expressed in proverbs, which in turn help people to understand the world and to learn from experience. In a few words proverbs explain human problems and behavior.

There are several types of proverbs:

Universal proverbs – On comparing proverbs of culturally unrelated parts of the world, one finds several ones having not only the same basic idea but the form of expression, i.e. the wording is also identical or very similar. These are mainly simple expressions of simple observations or simple ethical concepts, but not all expressions of simple observations became proverbs in every language.

Regional proverbs – In culturally related regions - on the pattern of loan-words - many loan-proverbs appear beside the indigenous ones. A considerable part of them can be traced back to the classical literature of the region's past, in Europe the Greco-Roman classics, and in the Far East to the Sanskrit and Korean classics.

Local Proverbs – In a cultural region often internal differences appear, the classics (e.g. the Bible or the Confucian Analects) are not equally regarded as a source of proverbs in every language. Geographical vicinity gives also rise to another set of common local proverbs.

Proverbs were always the most vivacious and at the same time the most stable part of the national languages, suitable competing with the sayings and aphorisms of outstanding thinkers. They express the outlook of the amount of people by their social and ideal functions. Proverbs and sayings include some certain features of historical development and the culture of people.

The semantic sphere of proverbs is very wide and cannot limit them. The proverbs describe every branch of people's life. The fact is that proverbs and sayings are similar in meaning in spite of their diversity in form and language.

3. Proverbs as the way of expressing peoples' wisdom and spirit.

Many people have loved proverbs for the wisdom embedded in them. Others have treasured proverbs for the vividness or earthiness of their imagery. But there is another characteristic of the proverb: its verbal economy. Proverbs are rarely wordy. The usual proverb is spare and austere in expression, and some are marvels of compactness.

“Wisdom” and “shortness” doubtlessly belong to the popular notion of what makes up a proverb. Dealing with national and international proverbs, we point out their cynicism, philosophy and humor, their obvious misogyny and their contradictory comments on life's experiences around the world:

Proverbs are among the most ancient of human institutions. Criticism of life, in brief and pithy form, is characteristic of proverbs, while their popular philosophy is indeed, proverbial.

“Proverbs are the wisdom of peoples” goes an Italian saying. This is perhaps an exaggeration, but there is no doubt that much of a nation's folk-philosophy gets into proverbs, along with the spice of national customs and, above all, the peculiar flavor of the nation's language and phraseology. Above all, they are the fruit of observation and inductive reasoning, two of the great faculties of the human mind. A generalization caught on, became popular, and was passed from mouth to mouth, from generation to

generation. Ultimately it became an integral part of the group's folklore, and was repeated whenever the situation it described recurred. Every proverb tells a story and teaches a lesson.

Proverbs come from a variety of sources. Some are, indeed, the result of people pondering and crafting language, such as some by Confucius, Plato, Baltasar Gracián, etc. Others are taken from such diverse sources as poetry, stories, songs, commercials, advertisements, movies, literature, etc. A number of the well known sayings of Jesus, Shakespeare, and others have become proverbs, though they were original at the time of their creation, and many of these sayings were not seen as proverbs when they were first coined. Many proverbs are also based on stories, often the end of a story. For example, the proverb “Who will bell the cat?” is from the end of a story about the mice planning how to be safe from the cat.

Some authors have created proverbs in their writings, such as J.R.R. Tolkien, and some of these proverbs have made their way into broader society. Similarly, C.S. Lewis' created proverb about a lobster in a pot, from the Chronicles of Narnia, has also gained currency. In cases like this, deliberately created proverbs for fictional societies have become proverbs in real societies. In a fictional story set in a real society, the movie Forrest Gump introduced “Life is like a box of chocolates” into broad society. In at least one case, it appears that a proverb deliberately created by one writer has been naively picked up and used by another who assumed it to be an established Chinese proverb, Ford Madox Ford having picked up a proverb from Ernest Bramah, “It would be hypocrisy to seek for the person of the Sacred Emperor in a Low Tea House.”

The proverb with “a longer history than any other recorded proverb in the world”, going back to “around 1800 BC” is in a Sumerian clay tablet, “The bitch by her acting too hastily brought forth the blind”. Though many proverbs are ancient, they were all newly created at some point by somebody. Sometimes it is easy to detect that a proverb is newly coined by a reference to something recent, such as the Haitian proverb “The fish that is being microwaved doesn't fear the lightning”. Similarly, there is a recent Maltese proverb, wil-muturi, ferh u duluri “Women and motorcycles are joys and griefs”; the proverb is clearly new, but still formed as a traditional style couplet with rhyme. Also, there is a proverb in the Kafa language of Ethiopia that refers to the forced military conscription of the 1980s, “...the one who hid himself lived to have children.” A Mongolian proverb also shows evidence of recent origin, “A beggar who sits on gold; Foam rubber piled on edge.” Another example of a proverb that is clearly recent is this from

Sesotho: “A mistake goes with the printer.” A political candidate in Kenya popularised a new proverb in his 1995 campaign, Chuth ber “Immediacy is best”. “The proverb has since been used in other contexts to prompt quick action.” Over 1,400 new English proverbs are said to have been coined and gained currency in the 20th century.

This process of creating proverbs is always ongoing, so that possible new proverbs are being created constantly. Those sayings that are adopted and used by an adequate number of people become proverbs in that society.

REFERENCES:

1. Momynova B. New directions and typical relations in the language. – Almaty: Arys, 2009. – 160 p.
2. Gurevitsch P.S. Anthropocentrism as philosophic position. Philosophical anthropology. – M., 2001. – 160 p.
3. Alpatov V.M. Wilhelm Humboldt. In Book: History of linguistic studies. Second edition. – M., 1999. – 368 p.
4. Orasbaeva F. Linguistic relation. – Almaty: Dictionary, 2005. – 272 p.
5. Gylyga A.V. German classical philosophy. – M., 1986. – 334 p.
6. Zhanpeisov E. Ethnocultural lexis of the Kazakh language. – Almaty: Science, 1989. – 282 p.
7. Zhaksybaeva M.A. Ethnographic phraseologisms of the Kazakh and Russian languages. Dissertation. – Almaty, 1997.
8. Kaidar A. Current problems of the Kazakh Language. – Almaty, 1998. – 304 p.
9. Mankeeva Zh.A. Cognitive fundamentals of ethnocultural concepts in the Kazakh language. – Almaty: Zhybek Zholy, 2008. – 354 p.
10. Tschesnokova N.V. Anthropocentric conception of works S.N.Sergeev –Tsenskogo: linguistic aspect: Dissertation. – Tambov, 2003.
11. Kubryakova E.S. Evolution of linguistic ideas in the Second part of XX century (paradigm analysis) //Language and Science of the end of XX century: Collection of articles. – M., 1995. – P. 144–238.